

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Obinna****FIRST NAME: Orjingene****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. All essay writing should include which of the following structure?

- Introduction, body, conclusion.¹
- Topic sentence, analysis, evidence, arguments.
- Drafting, road map, research questions, summary.
- Punctuation, paraphrasing, special instruction, guidelines.

2. In the use of style guide, which of these aspect are considered relevant?

- Frequency, inconsistency, concession, publication.
- Informal writing, use of paragraphs, quotation, the use of headings.
- Contributing authors, incoherency, authors considerations.
- Manuscript layout, font usage, spelling, use of symbols.²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 3.

² *Ibid.*, 24-25.

3. **In research, the following are tertiary sources of data?**
- Diaries, letters, manuscripts, film scripts.
 - Recordings, musical scores, books, articles
 - General encyclopedia, dictionaries, newspapers, magazines.**³
 - Observation, interviews, eye witness reports.
4. **All of the following key elements are core to a researcher's argument except?**
- Researchers claim.
 - Readers claim.**⁴
 - Reasons for accepting the claim.
 - Evidence that supports those reasons.
5. **When completing qualitative dissertation, which of the following is not one of the primary approaches in designing a qualitative study?**
- Philosophy.**⁵
 - Ethnography.
 - Grounded theory.
 - Case study.
6. **In the conduct of a qualitative study, developing a roadmap for a literature review entails which of the following?**

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 24-25.

⁴ Ibid., 37.

⁵ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, A Road Map from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications), 25.

- Synthesis, Review, development of the conceptual framework.**⁶
 - Identification and dissemination of the literature.
 - Review and publication.
 - Classification and cataloguing.
7. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, a book with two authors is referenced with which of the following formula? (pay attention to the punctuation or lack thereof presented in each possible answer)**
- Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Date. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
 - First Author's last name, first Author's first name, second Author's first and last names. Year of Publication. Title of Book:Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication Publisher's name.**⁷
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title (in quotation marks), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
8. **In the Turabian Author-Date citation style, for unpublished sourced material, the title is written in the following format ?**
- In parenthesis and capitalized.
 - In double quotation marks and italicized.
 - Double period, not punctuated.
 - In Roman type, enclosed in quotation marks, and not italicized.**⁸

⁶ Ibid., 51.

⁷ Turabian, 129.

⁸ Ibid., 150.

9. **The new date format for all full dates both in the text, footnotes and references, as recommended in the current edition of the Chicago Manual of Style is?**
- Year Month, Day.
 - Day Month, Year.
 - Month Day, Year.**⁹
 - Month Year, Day.
10. **In the use of Periods, Commas and Quotation Marks, the US standard recommend?**
- Periods and commas are always inside closing quotation marks.**¹⁰
 - Periods and commas are always outside closing quotation marks.
 - Quotation within a quotation.
 - Double period outside closing quotation marks.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 48.

¹⁰ Ibid., 35.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation, A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.